

The Effects of Turkey's Foreign Policy on Exports in the Last 15 Years

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Abstract

In the global context, economics and politics are interdependent phenomena. A multitude of activities is contingent upon politics. Political issues or disputes between nations preclude the possibility of accessing a market. The export process is influenced by the relationships between nations. Our commercial links with the Middle East and Russia have been sustained historically. Nevertheless, Turkey has been unable to sustain uninterrupted economic operations in the designated regions at various intervals. The notion of soft power has influenced global politics since the Cold War. Global politics and economics are governed by cultural and economic activity. The Turkish Foreign Policy influences Turkey's export procedures. Prior to the Arab Spring, Turkey's approach to the Middle East and Syria was distinct. The alteration in Foreign Policy concerning the Middle East and Syria has diminished Turkey's export rate to these regions. Additional elucidations are available in other sections of the article about this topic. The notion of risk is used to elucidate international politics and economics. Social, political, and economic conditions delineate risk at certain intervals. I shall elucidate the risk factor associated with the Russian Aircraft Crisis instance.

Keywords: *Foreign Relations, Economy, Trade, Middle East, Turkish Russian Relations, Soft Power, Turkish Foreign Policy, Diplomacy*

Introduction

My study delineates the impact of Turkish Foreign Policy on its exports during the last 15 years. Major nations globally use soft power. States influence the global landscape via economic activities, commerce, cultural exchanges, and other means. This article will elucidate Soft Power, Turkish Foreign Policy, and Turkey's diplomatic ties with Syria, Iraq, Iran, Russia, and the Organization of Islamic Cooperation in depth. I shall elucidate the economic ramifications of Turkey's shift in stance about Syria, introduce the notion of risk, examine the aircraft problem with Russia, and end my piece.

Alongside their political dominance, major nations use soft power to attain economic sovereignty. Economy, culture, and commerce serve as significant instruments for global influence. Turkey's favorable diplomatic connections with several nations historically have broadened its export network. The expanding export network has enhanced economic circumstances. Turkey's shift in stance over Syria and its issue with Russia have had adverse consequences. This is elucidated comprehensively with illustrations in my paper.

Soft Power

Experts describe Soft Power in many ways. It is presented as economics, culture, and diplomacy. I shall analyze this topic using theories, occurrences, and case studies. Joseph S. Nye posits that power is the capacity to persuade others to get desired outcomes (Çağlar, Ermihan and Görür, 2020). Certain nations use armed action to attain their objectives and secure desired positions (Çağlar, Ermihan and Görür, 2020). Soft power is a notion that has arisen in recent years. This authority encompasses the economy (Çağlar, Ermihan and Görür, 2020). Certain governments cultivate commercial and economic links with others to exert influence (Çağlar, Ermihan and Görür, 2020). Their economic standing enables them to impact the internal policy of other states (Çağlar, Ermihan and Görür, 2020). Certain states possess distinct charms and reputation (Çağlar, Ermihan and Görür, 2020). They use their charisma and status to affect the internal policy of other nations (Çağlar, Ermihan and Görür, 2020). This example illustrates soft power (Çağlar, Ermihan and Görür, 2020). There are three categories of soft power ideas (Çağlar, Ermihan and Görür, 2020).

Countries first establish their suitable positions; then, they acquire soft power via the use of political ideals (Çağlar, Ermihan, & Görür, 2020).

Secondly, a nation may acquire soft power via foreign policy whenever it is acknowledged as a legitimate authority by other nations (Çağlar, Ermihan, & Görür, 2020). Third, soft power may be attained by cultural values that appeal to other nations (Çağlar, Ermihan, & Görür, 2020).

In contemporary society, soft power is used in commercial endeavors. While Türkiye employs the notion of soft power politically, it has, in some instances, used it in aggressive tactics for almost a decade. This procedure results in financial detriment.

Turkey employs the notion of culture as a kind of soft power (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). Turkey has embraced Ottoman culture (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). Ottoman culture is evident in everyday life and diplomatic interactions (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). As the use of military force to acquire sovereignty is not endorsed by other nations, soft power is employed (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). With the advancement of collaboration and democracy in contemporary society, the acquisition of influence via soft power has gained significance (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). Through the use of soft power, nations are drawn in, eliminating the need for conventional force (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). While the use of soft power may not be rapid or efficient, it may provide lasting and impactful results if employed deliberately and effectively (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). Following the conclusion of the Cold War, Turkey has prioritized the use of soft power (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). As of 2019, Turkey is recognized as one of the nation's using the notion of soft power globally (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). It is positioned twenty-ninth out of thirty nations, with a rate of 49.7% (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). Turkey aspires to be a regional power, enhancing its global impact and intensifying its activities for over two decades (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). To attain this objective, it forges historical and cultural connections with Middle Eastern nations (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). Turkey endeavors to assume mediator positions among these nations (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). Turkey forged alliances with various factions to enhance its influence over nations during the Arab Spring and adopted the donor country model in response to humanitarian disasters (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). Turkey has used soft power in both Arab and African nations (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). It has invested in cultural and economic sectors and executed development initiatives to enhance its impact on the African continent (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). Turkey has established forty-two embassies in Africa and conducted commerce amounting to 23 million dollars with these nations (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). Since 1992, Turkey has awarded scholarships to 10,480 African students (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). In 2018, investments totaled 46 million dollars (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). Furthermore, during the 2017 dispute between Qatar and the Gulf states, Turkey assumed a mediatory role (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). Turkey engaged in discussions with the Gulf nations (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). This endeavor did not normalize ties, however the relationship between Qatar and Turkey improved (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). In addition, owing to Turkey's economic ties with Iran and the impact of sanctions related to Iran's nuclear armament, Western nations, in 2010, facilitated mediation with Brazil to address the dispute between Russia and Iran (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). Turkey employs soft power as a

mediator to maintain its peaceful role and safeguard its economic interests (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). In the first decade, Turkey prioritized soft power in its international relations, resulting in favorable outcomes (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). The TİKA Middle East 2010 Reports indicate that soft power initiatives directed toward Middle Eastern nations enhanced Turkey's appeal and elevated its prominence in economic, political, and cultural domains (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). The predominance of a Muslim population and the democratic governance of Turkey make it appealing in international relations (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). The influence of soft power is seen in Turkish television series and tourism (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). Turkish television programs are seen by neighboring nations, fostering favorable perceptions of Turkey (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). Due to cultural commonalities, Turkish television shows have gained popularity and drawn an increasing number of international visitors to our nation (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). Turkey is favored by international visitors, the majority of whom see our television series (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). Turkish television shows are seen in Middle Eastern nations (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). Soft power yields beneficial outcomes. Its impact is increasingly becoming lasting with each passing day. The assurance of military might cannot last indefinitely (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020).

Consequently, due to the unsuccessful outcome of the Arab Spring, Turkey's foreign policy initiatives failed to achieve the intended objectives (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). The regional populace's affection for Turkey has diminished (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). This phenomenon is also seen along the axis of Egypt and Syria (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020).

Turkey and the Gulf States

A problem exists between Çağlar, Ermihan, and Görür (2020). The influence of Turkey over the Gulf nations is waning (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). The plight of Syrian refugees has generated friction between Turkey and the European Union (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). Following the onset of the Covid-19 epidemic that impacted the whole globe, Turkey implemented constructive measures (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). Turkey has provided assistance to Europe and other areas via several organizations to enhance cooperation (Çağlar, Ermihan, Görür, 2020). Turkey provides assistance via TİKA, the Organization for Turks Abroad and Related Communities, and the Yunus Emre Institute (Çağlar, Ermihan, & Görür,

2020). These three institutions are crucial in advancing Turkey's soft power and cultural diplomacy (Çağlar, Ermihan, & Görür, 2020). The actions of TIKA and YTB are contingent upon the cultural foreign policy established by the government (Çağlar, Ermihan, & Görür, 2020). TIKA supplied food assistance to Muslims residing in the Granada area of Spain during Ramadan (Çağlar, Ermihan, & Görür, 2020). Furthermore, Turkey supplied food and sanitary products to nations in Africa, Europe, Asia, and the Middle East (Çağlar, Ermihan, & Görür, 2020).

YTB assisted 165,549 individuals across 14 nations during the Covid-19 pandemic. Furthermore, it inaugurated a mask factory in France (Çağlar, Ermihan, & Görür, 2020). The Yunus Emre Institute executed educational initiatives in a digital setting (Çağlar, Ermihan, & Görür, 2020). The Yunus Emre Institute offered online Turkish language lessons as a component of its cultural diplomacy initiatives in Australia and New Zealand (Çağlar, Ermihan, & Görür, 2020). The Covid-19 Hub platform was established to disseminate information on the coronavirus epidemic (Çağlar, Ermihan, & Görür, 2020).

In addition to this, Turkey provided medical assistance to other NATO nations, including the USA, England, Spain, and Italy (Çağlar, Ermihan and Görür, 2020). Furthermore, assistance was sent to Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Montenegro, North Macedonia, and Serbia (Çağlar, Ermihan and Görür, 2020). Turkey participated in the assistance initiative established by the European Commission, which was well received by Commission President Von Der Leyen (Çağlar, Ermihan and Görür, 2020). Nevertheless, Turkey executed misguided foreign policies that resulted in a decline in export rates. Inappropriate policies may also influence domestic politics. If the export rate does not align with the import rate, residents will struggle to locate a variety of items. When the export rate fails to align with the import rate, the country's inflation rate escalates, resulting in a decline in buying power. The nation is also incapable of generating economic resources. I shall elucidate the significance of foreign policy concerning the export circumstances of nations.

Results of Turkish Foreign Policy

Turkey's foreign policy has influenced export rates. As per the January 2016 statistics data released by the Turkish statistics Institute, several experts express apprehensions about the Turkish economy (Danışoğlu, 2016). Exports in 2015 were reduced relative to 2014

(Danışoğlu, 2016). Foreign policy has served as an instrument for international commerce for years (Danışoğlu, 2016). Historically, nations have appropriated foreign trade routes from competitors to enhance their economic advantages (Danışoğlu, 2016). Moreover, nations have confiscated and destroyed the commercial vessels of other nations by piracy (Danışoğlu, 2016). Furthermore, international agreements have provisions prohibiting trading with foreign nations (Danışoğlu, 2016). Recent embargoes have also been instituted (Danışoğlu, 2016). Furthermore, several nations have used free trade zones and customs unions as strategies to enhance trade channels (Danışoğlu, 2016). Foreign policy strategies have been used to enhance international commerce and diminish the foreign trade of competing nations (Danışoğlu, 2016). The study from the Turkish Statistical Institute indicates that Turkey's exports to adjacent countries have been declining for many years (Danışoğlu, 2016). I shall explain by nation.

Russia

We have engaged in prolonged confrontation with Russia (Danışoğlu, 2016). Turkey's export rate to Russia declined after 2013, despite previously exporting several commodities to the country (Danışoğlu, 2016). Turkey's exports to Russia declined by 48 percent from 2013 to 2015 (Danışoğlu, 2016). The export rate declined to 66 percent in 2016. The export rate of Turkey declined with the Commonwealth of Independent States (Danışoğlu, 2016). The states include Azerbaijan, Armenia, Belarus, Kazakhstan, Moldova, Kyrgyzstan, Russia, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, and Ukraine (Danışoğlu, 2016). In 2016, the export rate to the Commonwealth of Independent States declined to 49 percent (Danışoğlu, 2016).

Egypt

Exports to Egypt increased in 2012, but then declined after the coup in 2013 (Danışoğlu, 2016). The collapse of the Muslim Brotherhood administration in Egypt impacted the economic connections between the two nations (Danışoğlu, 2016). The export rate from Turkey to Egypt has declined to 15%. Subsequently, Turkey's export rate to North African nations decreased to 15% from 2013 to 2015 (Danışoğlu, 2016).

Iraq

Iraq is a significant market for Turkey (Danışoğlu, 2016). Turkey's export rate to Iraq was favorable till 2013 (Danışoğlu, 2016). Following the ISIS assault on Samarra, a civil war ensued in Iraq (Danışoğlu, 2016). Throughout this era, the Iraqi government sought to discontinue its contacts with Turkey (Danışoğlu, 2016). Turkey's export rate to Iraq declined to 28% from 2013 to 2015 (Danışoğlu, 2016). Subsequently, the export rate between Turkey and Iraq persisted in its decrease (Danışoğlu, 2016).

Syria

Turkey was exporting several commodities to Syria (Danışoğlu, 2016). In 2010, Turkey's exports to this nation amounted to 1.85 billion dollars (Danışoğlu, 2016). A civil conflict erupted in Syria in 2011 (Danışoğlu, 2016). Subsequently, as a result of this circumstance, exports between the two nations ceased (Danışoğlu, 2016).

Organization of Islamic Cooperation

Turkey's issues with Iraq, Syria, Egypt, Libya, and Yemen impact its exports to the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (Danışoğlu, 2016). The export rate of Turkey to the members of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation was 30 percent (Danışoğlu, 2016). Subsequently, post-2012, there was a decline in the export rate to these nations (Danışoğlu, 2016). From 2012 to 2015, Turkey's export rate to these nations declined to 23 percent (Danışoğlu, 2016).

The facts and ratios indicate that Turkey's foreign policy has adversely impacted its export process and economy (Danışoğlu, 2016). These measures were enacted during an international crisis (Danışoğlu, 2016). Turkey pursued alternative markets to address economic challenges (Danışoğlu, 2016).

overseas policies concerning Russia, Syria, Iraq, and Egypt demonstrate that strong responses or developing wars between nations impact economies, overseas commerce, and export rates. Disputes with some nations impact not just the bilateral relations but also the dynamics with other states. Russia's influence in the Commonwealth of Independent States has impacted

Turkey's export operations with these nations. The aviation conflict with Russia has resulted in enduring economic consequences for Turkey. This article will explain the situation in further depth within the context of the Russian situation Case.

Relations with Syria after the Arab Spring

Turkey's connections with the West have mostly influenced its foreign policy with the Middle East and Syria (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). Until the 1950s, Turkey deemed it more prudent to refrain from intervening in Middle Eastern matters due to security apprehensions (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). Turkey saw the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics as a danger and thus aligned with the West to further its national goals (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). Turkey's security apprehensions influenced its foreign policy until the 2000s (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). Alterations in worldwide and regional dynamics prompted Turkey's engagement in the area throughout the 2000s (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013).

Turkey's Middle East strategy and its ties with Syria underwent transformation in the early 2000s (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). Turkey was executing Middle East policy over the objections of the US and the West (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). In the early 2000s, Turkey provided help to Syria (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). Following the resolution of the trustworthiness issue with Syria, a model neighborhood relationship was established between these nations (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). Syria serves as Turkey's conduit to the Middle East (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). In December 2009, 51 collaboration agreements were signed (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). The High Level Strategic Cooperation Council was formed between Turkey and Syria (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). To enhance collaboration between the border provinces of Turkey and Syria, the Interregional Cooperation Program was initiated, and the Joint Monitoring and Steering Committee was formed (Karakoyun, Özbek and Demircan, 2013).

Modifications in Turkey's Middle East strategy prompted a heightened emphasis on regional issues (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). Consequently, Turkey increased its engagement and facilitated the advancement of commercial links with regional nations (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). The Arab Spring adversely impacted Turkey's initiatives in the Middle East and Syria (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). The military engagement in response to anti-regime demonstrations adversely affected societal

stability and incited conflicts (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). A significant number of individuals perished in this fight (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). Turkey actively participated in the Syrian Crisis (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). The upheavals in Syria altered the amicable ties between Turkey and Syria (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). The political instability and violence in Syria adversely impacted economic links with neighboring countries, resulting in a significant influx of migrants to Turkey (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). Consequently, this circumstance resulted in adverse economic and social repercussions in Turkey and its regional regions (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013).

In 2011, Turkey's export value amounted to 137 billion USD (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). Trade with Syria constituted 1.6 billion dollars of this total sum (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). Nonetheless, the impacts were more pronounced in the border provinces at that period. The crisis resulted in a decline in economic activity in our border provinces (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). The issues resulted in diminished production, export, employment, and market presence in the border cities involved in the commercial interaction with the Middle East via Syria (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). The evolving economic and political connections between Turkey and Syria, together with the abolition of visas, have facilitated Syria's importation of products from Turkey (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). Economic activity have notably increased, particularly in border cities such Hatay, Adana, Gaziantep, Kilis, Şanlıurfa, and Mardin (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013).

In the 2000s, Turkey instituted the "Zero Problems with Neighbors Policy," which positively influenced international commerce (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). A prominent instance of this approach was Syria (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). Political issues were being resolved, and commerce among these nations was facilitated during that period (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). Three significant agreements were executed among these nations (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). In 2004, these nations signed agreements on the Avoidance of Double Taxation, Reciprocal Promotion and Protection of Investments, and Free Trade (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). The Free Trade Agreement among these nations became effective in 2007 (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). This agreement enhanced economic cooperation, removed trade obstacles, established an advantageous competitive position, and highlighted investment incentives (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). Analysis of international commerce between Turkey and Syria

from 2005 to 2011 reveals a growth in import and export rates as well as foreign trade capacity (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013).

Turkey altered its foreign policy against Syria and initiated economic and financial sanctions in 2011 (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). As a result of this circumstance, trade ties among these nations started to decline (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013).

Turkey's exports to Syria amounted to 552 million dollars in 2005 and escalated to 1 billion 610 million dollars in 2011 (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). Export rates surged by 192 percent during a six-year period (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). In 2005, the proportion of Turkey's exports to Syria relative to the General Export Rate was 0.8% (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013), which rose to 1.6% in 2010 (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). Following the implementation of the Free Trade Agreement in 2007, the export rate among these nations escalated (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). In 2010, Syria purchased a greater volume of commodities from Turkey than from any other nation (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). The province of Istanbul was the first region to import products to Syria (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). The export performance of Şanlıurfa has improved due to its links with Syria. In 2005, Şanlıurfa's export value was under one million dollars, but it rose by 34 million dollars in 2008 (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). Numerous provinces had a rise in export rates till 2010 (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). Nevertheless, the export rates of provinces such Kocaeli, Ankara, Konya, and Bursa declined in 2011 (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). From 2005 to 2011, Turkey mostly sold coal, refined petroleum products, and nuclear fuel to Syria (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013).

Turkey's imports from Syria rose from 143 million dollars in 2005 to 337 million dollars in 2011 (Karakoyun, Özbek and Demircan, 2013). The import rate in six years is 36% (Karakoyun, Özbek and Demircan, 2013). Nonetheless, the rise in imports was less than the rise in exports (Karakoyun, Özbek and Demircan, 2013). In 2010, Turkey emerged as the fourth largest importer from Syria (Karakoyun, Özbek and Demircan, 2013). Numerous cities, including İzmir, İstanbul, Kocaeli, Kayseri, Denizli, and Kahramanmaraş, import a greater volume from Syria.

Karakoyun, Özbek, and Demircan (2013). Turkey was importing coal, refined petroleum products, nuclear fuel, and textile goods from Syria (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013).

Turkey began the implementation of economic and financial sanctions on Syria in 2011 (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). The sanctions affected international commerce (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). In 2012, Turkey's exports decreased to 70% and imports declined to 80% (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). The intensification of hostilities between Turkey and Syria has adversely impacted the economies of Turkey, its border regions, and other nations (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). The conflicts among these nations have impacted exports not just to Syria but also to other Middle Eastern countries (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013). The conflict among these nations has hindered investment prospects in several areas, including Şanlıurfa, Mardin, and Şırnak (Karakoyun, Özbek, & Demircan, 2013).

The alteration in Turkey's stance against Syria, akin to the situation with Russia, is the primary determinant in the decline of its economic engagements. Turkey's inability to effectively export its exports has resulted in a prolonged deficiency of economic resources. Throughout the conflict, Turkey provided more assistance to the opposition organizations than to the Syrian government. The political shift also influenced Turkey's ties with the Middle East. Consequently, the repercussions have been experienced for years.

Definition of Risk in Politics and Economics

The notion of risk is extensively used in finance, economics, and strategic management. Miller (1992) posits that causal outcomes and performance variations pertain to risk. Organizations face internal and external influences, leading to the emergence of the idea of risk. Risk ideas and risk sources exist (Can, Özmutlu, Aykaç, 2019). For instance, the origins of risks and their contributing aspects are delineated by political risk and competitive risk elements (Can, Özmutlu, Aykaç, 2019). The whims and unpredictable external factors influencing organizational performance are elucidated by these two notions (Can, Özmutlu, Aykaç, 2019). Political risk arises from instability (Can, Özmutlu, Aykaç, 2019). Political risk encompasses the risk associated with specific occurrences, including government interventions and changes in political systems, as well as several other events (Can, Özmutlu, Aykaç, 2019). Political risk influences international commerce and delineates the level of risk (Can, Özmutlu, Aykaç, 2019). Truitt (1974) defines political risk as the danger associated with inaction and unemployment. Political risk necessitates an extensive procedure accompanied by a long-term

strategic outlook (Fitzpatrick, 1983, p.252). Political ties across nations do not always develop in a linear manner. Should political connections decline owing to disparities across nations, new risk factors arise (Can, Özmutlu, Aykaç, 2019). Compensation for political risk is the catalyst for emerging crises (Can, Özmutlu, Aykaç, 2019). To discuss the political risk element, one must understand the conceptual meaning of the crisis (Can, Özmutlu, Aykaç, 2019). A crisis is a condition of instability and peril that induces alterations in social, economic, political, and international domains (Can, Özmutlu, Aykaç, 2019). Tüz (1996) posits that crises embody chaos, whereby some parties emerge victorious while others suffer losses. The onset of chaos signifies instability. Political instability pertains to the management and maintenance of societal order.

It elucidates the precarious position that arises due to the disruption of fundamental prerequisites for a certain duration (Can, Özmutlu, Aykaç, 2019). An imbalance is evident in Turkish-Russian ties. International, multinational, and global organizations must be prepared for crises in both host and primary nations. Uncertainties impact job operations and induce instabilities. Miller (1992) categorizes uncertainty into many forms, including political, governmental policies, macroeconomic, social, and natural instability. Daniell (2000) analyzes uncertainty across four dimensions. Daniell (2000) categorizes uncertainties into financial, cultural, legal, and political concerns. Political, economic, and social developments result in uncertainty (Can, Özmutlu, Aykaç, 2019). Political uncertainty often include changes in political regimes (Shubik, 1983). War, revolution, and political strife generate uncertainty (Can, Özmutlu, Aykaç, 2019).

Instabilities in state politics may influence the business climate (Ting, 1988). Political uncertainties generate political dangers (Can, Özmutlu, Aykaç, 2019). Fiscal and monetary reforms, price regulation, trade restrictions, state control, and nationalization may induce concerns inside the state (Miller, 1992).

Macroeconomic uncertainty include economic operations and pricing (Oxelheim and Whilborg, 1987). Price currencies, overall price inflation, fluctuations in input costs, and consumer products prices elucidate macroeconomic uncertainty (Can, Özmutlu, Aykaç, 2019). Fluctuations in output and pricing are associated with fluctuations in interest rates and currency rates (Can, Özmutlu, Aykaç, 2019). Purchasing power parity, fluctuations in exchange rates, supply sources, and product price might provide arbitrage possibilities for international corporations (Miller, 1992).

Social uncertainty may pertain to both social and political ambiguities (Can, Özmutlu, Aykaç, 2019). Social uncertainties manifest in social unrest, riots, and small terrorist acts (Can, Özmutlu, Aykaç, 2019). Should such catastrophes pose challenges for nations, political ambiguities may emerge in these instances (Miller, 1992).

Natural uncertainties include phenomena that influence economic production (Can, Özmutlu, Aykaç, 2019). Inherent unpredictability is evident in the agriculture industry (Can, Özmutlu, Aykaç, 2019). Climatic factors influence production. (Can, Özmutlu, Aykaç, 2019) Moreover, natural catastrophes may adversely affect corporate operations, hence diminishing production capacity (Miller, 1992).

Russian Aircraft Crisis

Moreover, Turkey has maintained political and economic links with Russia throughout history. While ties rely on peace and cooperation among these nations, there have been notable outliers in their interactions (Büyükkakıncı; 2012). Consequently, there has been no consistent advancement in the ties between Turkey and Russia. Relations have further worsened, particularly after the airstrikes conducted by Russia in Northern Syria (BBC, 2015). Subsequent to the bombing crisis, commercial ties between Turkey and Russia were favorable (Can, Özmutlu, Aykaç, 2019). Following the disruption of the global equilibrium, economic interactions among these nations enhanced (Can, Özmutlu, Aykaç, 2019). Turkish officials said that Russia breached its airspace and downed the aircraft despite issuing a warning to the Russian authorities (BBC, 2015). One Russian pilot perished in the incident, while another sustained injuries and was rescued (BBC, 2015). Turkish officials said that all parties must respect Turkey's right to safeguard its borders. Turkish officials affirmed that Turkey supported opposition factions in Syria (BBC, 2015).

Subsequently, Russian President Vladimir Putin said that the destruction of the Russian aircraft was attributable to the actions of the two nations (BBC, 2015). Additionally, Russian Foreign Minister Sergey Lavrov advised Russian people from traveling to Turkey (BBC, 2015). Certain travel organizations have annulled excursions to Turkey (BBC, 2015). Armed Forces of the

Russian Federation

The commander severed all military communication with Türkiye (BBC, 2015). Sergey Lavrov cautioned Russian nationals in Turkey to repatriate to Russia (BBC, 2015). Putin instructed Russian Prime Minister Medvedev to implement sanctions on Turkey (BBC, 2015). During that period, Turkish lorries were halted at the Russian border (BBC, 2015).

Prior to the aviation crisis, ties between Turkey and Russia were favorable (Can, Özmutlu, Aykaç, 2019). Prior to the crisis, the significance of economic and political ties has escalated (Can, Özmutlu, Aykaç, 2019). Turkey exported coffee, tea, cocoa, spices, travel goods, bags, footwear, fruits and vegetables, apparel, motor vehicles, bicycles, motorcycles, fertilizers for animals and plants, salt, sulfur, prefabricated structures, plumbing supplies, heating and fixed lighting apparatus, textile goods, electricity generation machinery, fish and seafood, medical and pharmaceutical products, and furniture to Russia (Can, Özmutlu, Aykaç, 2019). The sanctions enacted by the Russian Government encompass the cessation of certain food exports, the imposition of restrictions on Turkish enterprises, the suspension of tourism to Turkey, the cancellation of select flights, the revocation of visa-free travel, and the inspection of trucks originating from Turkey and vessels arriving from the Black Sea (BBC, 2015). Russia declared a list of items that would no longer be imported from Turkey (BBC, 2015). Tomatoes, citrus fruits, and poultry goods will not be imported to Russia (BBC, 2015). Agricultural commodities including tomatoes, onions, cauliflower, broccoli, cucumbers, oranges, tangerines, other citrus fruits, apples, grapes, pears, peaches, apricots, plums, strawberries, and cloves were prohibited from importation from Turkey (BBC, 2015). Chicken, turkey, and salt were further included on the list of prohibited items (BBC, 2015). A solitary aggressive action by Turkey precipitated a diplomatic crisis. In times of crises with other nations, governments may use economic sanctions as a response. Even if commercial connections between two nations are severed, the conflict between them might impact trade relations with other nations. The situation involving Russia has impacted Turkey's ties with the Commonwealth of Independent States. Certain items must be shipped to other nations via Russia. This problem may be elucidated by the case of Syria.

Conclusion

Consequently, the notion of soft power is used in foreign policy. Countries often seek to acquire power via economic endeavors and cultural influence. Countries, however, react to crises by imposing economic penalties on other nations. Economic penalties may have enduring consequences. Countries face significant challenges in exporting commodities to other nations during a catastrophe. I referenced the risk factor in my paper. The social, political, and economic domains include the risk factor. Political events, geopolitical crises, and natural calamities might precipitate hazards. Economic success cannot be sustained indefinitely due to the potential for numerous threats to impede it. Certain years have seen favorable ties between nations. The circumstances are elucidated by the instances of Syria, the Middle East, and Russia. Prior to the Arab Spring, Turkey was exporting several items to Syria and the Middle East. Turkey maintained favorable ties with both the Syrian and Russian governments. The alteration in Turkey's foreign policy toward the Syrian regime affected the economics of Turkey's border regions. Turkey traditionally exported goods from its border districts to Syria. Turkey has cultivated its political and economic links with Russia. Turkey was engaged in shipping items to Syria while simultaneously addressing global challenges. The airplane crisis adversely impacted Turkey's export rate, since the majority of its items were supplied to Russia. Identifying a market to enhance export rates is a challenging endeavor. Enhanced commercial links may be achieved via prolonged efforts. One party may exert influence over other states on market matters. Consequently, when the opposing party is unable to generate sufficient revenue owing to a decreased export rate, this circumstance may adversely impact internal policy.

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